

Thematic Study on Food Politics in India during Vedic period and 21st century

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ABSTRACT

India's food politics have changed dramatically between the Vedic era and the twenty first century, mirroring larger social, political, and economic shifts. In the Vedic era (1500–500 BCE), eating customs were closely linked to cultural and religious standards. Access to food was impacted by social stratification, and the Vedas, especially the Rigveda, mention food offerings as essential to rites. There were sacrifice rites and certain cuisines that were only available to the brahminical class, whereas the other castes had few culinary options. Agricultural systems were also established during this time, which had an impact on food distribution and land control. Despite advancements, problems like hunger, malnutrition, and regional disparities still exist, and caste, class, and political power continue to play a role in food politics in India. Globalisation, economic liberalisation, and urbanisation have all contributed to the complexity of food politics in the twenty-first century. The emergence of multinational food corporations, the move to processed foods, and government policies regarding food security like the National Food Security Act have also changed the way food is distributed and accessed.

KEY WORDS: Food politics, Vedic period, Rigveda, Varnas system, Government, Public Distribution System, Religion, purity and pollution, Agriculture, Discrimination, Vegetarianism and Non - Vegetarianism, Hygiene, FSSAI, Culture.

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INTRODUCTION

Food has been one of the most visible expressions of hierarchy and power in India. Food politics is the politicization of food in all aspects from production, distribution and consumption of food within the country. It encompasses the issues related to the division of food based on the influence of caste and religion, role of agriculture, food sovereignty, Governments role in regulating food safety and nutrition labels during Vedic period and 21st century in India.

The map of Indian cuisine is mosaic of cooking methods, spice palates, and common ingredients that change from state to state and culture to culture. From coconut-rich foods popular in the southern state of Kerala to northern Rajasthan's famously spicy dishes, regional cuisines in India can vary widely.

The production and sale of food is an extremely big business and touches people in all industries and walks of life. Food is not only crucial for day-to-day survival, but also strongly affects overall health and well-being, as well as the economy and culture of a region or a country. Considering India as vast and diverse population, food politics plays a significant role in shaping public health and social equity. Food production and consumption in India have been the subject of numerous disputes and controversies over the years, including state-by-state meat bans and farmer demonstrations in Punjab and Uttar Pradesh. Islam and Christianity, for example, are frequently associated with meat and non-vegetarian cuisine, which perpetuates the myth that followers of these faiths are incapable of eating vegetarianism and will constantly cook non-vegetarian meals at home.

Food implicates matters of production, reproduction, distribution, consumption and the interlinkages between global, national and local scales. Food also incorporates questions of economy, state-society relations, and environment, as well as intimate issues of personal, social, cultural and bodily

status and identity So, food provides a vital lens through which to integrate and address a range of contemporary development challenges. Yet food is also a political matter, with questions of how food systems are constituted, how they change (or do not change), and who gains or loses implicating power relations of many kinds, between diverse actors.

The present study consists of politics behind the street food vendors in India which is acting as a booming business, as majority of the population run behind the spot on the streets to grab the food at affordable price. This has created a stress for restaurants and hotels who gets paid by less population for their food. Non -Vegetarian plays a dominant role in street food when compared to vegetarian food.

Street food politics in the 21st century has become a significant topic due to the increasing urbanization, globalization, and the evolving nature of food systems and regulations. As street food continues to play an essential role in many cultures, its political dimensions are shaped by several factors, including economics, labor, urban space, health, and sustainability. In the 21st century, these dynamics have been influenced by the changing relationship between informal economies and formal structures, as well as by global trends like gentrification, food security concerns, and environmental sustainability.

This analysis of food politics in India across these two periods highlights the changing dynamics of food security, class struggles, and cultural values, illustrating how food continues to be a site of contestation and power.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

Food politics is crucial due to its complex relationship with the society in terms of cultural, social and governing aspects. India is democratic country where politics play an important role in all aspects of life. As such food is considered as a basic necessity for existence which should also be viewed through the lens politics. Through this study analyses the challenges and nuances of politicization of food in India and how the food is fractionated based

on caste, religion and culture. So, this study is undertaken to analyse how forward the government is to take action to eliminate inequality in particular to food with several initiatives and policies.

Objectives of the Study

The aim is to explore Food Politics in India during Vedic period and 21st century:

- To understand the divisions of food based on religious and caste factors.
- Investigate the political influences shaping India's food systems.
- Exploring the connections between nutrition and public health.
- Analyze the effectiveness of Government interventions in ensuring food policies.

Related literature

- Food politics is a critical topic to analyse the needs of the society and the policies of government, thus several documented sources have been helpful for us while strategizing our research project. This book (FOOD POLITICS" by Robert Paarlberg) is reviewed for understanding the overview of food politics, consumption and future food politics.
- **"NO MEAT REQUIRED": The Cultural History and Culinary future for Plant based Eating by Aliciya Kennedy.** This book is reviewed for figuring out how to position vegetarian and vegan diets in political perspectives.

Other Articles which were reviewed for furthering our research work are:

- Caste: **"The main character of Indian food"** article written by **Rajini Kashyap.**

- **“Rousseau and Food”** article was written by **Kelly Oliver**
Department of Philosophy, Vanderbilt University, Nashville, TN,
USA.
- **“Plato and Food”** article was written by **Daniel Silvermintz** School
of Human Science and Humanities, University of Houston.
- **What could Food is Political mean?** Article written by **Aliciy Kennedy**.

DEFENITION OF THE TERM USED FOR THE STUDY:

VEDIC PERIOD: This period begins from 1500- 600 BCE. The term veda refers to the sacred knowledge which is contained in vedic texts. They are recognized not only as scriptures but also as the source of Indian culture and human civilization. There are four vedas: Rigveda, Samaveda, Yajurveda and Atharvaveda. Here Rig veda is the oldest veda and this veda emancipated the varna system which is categorized on the basis of occupation.

21st CENTURY: The 21st century is the current century, spanning from January 1, 2001, to December 31, 2100. It is the first century of the 3rd millennium and is characterized by significant technological innovation.

FOOD POLITICS: Food politics is the politicization of food in all aspects from production, distribution and consumption of food within the country. The production and sale of food is an extremely big business and touches people in all industries and walks of life. Food is not only crucial for day-to-day survival, but also strongly affects overall health and well-being, as well as the economy and culture of a region or a country. Considering India as vast and diverse population, food politics plays a significant role in shaping public health and social equity.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research dwells into exploratory design, which postulates the politicization of food in India specifically during from vedic period to 21st

century. The explanatory method and the descriptive design in this study highlights the issues relating to caste, religion and community.

SOURCE OF DATA: Our work also referring surveys, reports, previous studies and articles.

SECONDARY DATA:

The study deals with secondary data in view of the fact of its analytical and deductive method in nature. Our work also consists of surveys, reports, previous studies and articles.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

1. **Temporal Focus:** Vedic Period (c. 1500–500 BCE): The study will explore food-related practices, dietary norms, agricultural policies (if any), socio-religious influences, and the role of food in the caste and class system during the Vedic era.

21st Century (Post-2000 India): The study will focus on current food policies, agricultural reforms, food subsidies, food security, globalization, corporate influence, and debates around GMOs, organic farming, and climate-related impacts.

2. **Themes and Areas of Comparison:** Policy and Governance: How food was regulated or governed in both eras, including religious texts in the Vedic period versus governmental institutions and laws today.

Access and Distribution: Caste-based or class-based access to food historically versus economic and social barriers today. Religious and Cultural Influence:

Role of food in rituals, taboos, and religious prescriptions then and now.

Agricultural Practices: Techniques, tools, and crops in the Vedic period versus modern mechanized and industrial farming. Food as a Political Tool:

Symbolism, power dynamics, and control over food resources in both periods.

3. Sources Used:

- Ancient texts like the Vedas, Upanishads, and commentaries for the Vedic period.
- Government reports, policy documents, journal articles, media sources, and academic studies for the 21st century.
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LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. Historical Data Gaps:

- The Vedic period is reconstructed primarily through religious and philosophical texts, which are interpretive and often symbolic, lacking precise empirical data.
- No central administrative records or food policy documents from the Vedic period are available for direct comparison.

2. Interpretation Bias:

- Reliance on secondary interpretations of ancient texts may introduce scholarly bias or inconsistency.
- Religious texts were not written with political analysis in mind, so drawing parallels to modern food politics involves some speculation.

3. Incommensurability:

- The socio-political structures of the Vedic period (tribal or early kingdom) and the modern nation-state are vastly different, making direct comparisons limited in depth.
- Concepts like "policy" and "politics" had different meanings or forms in ancient times.

EVOLUTION OF FOOD FROM INDUS VALLEY CIVILISATION TO VEDIC PERIOD

The decline of the Indus Valley Civilization was followed by the Vedic period. During this period, the north-western region of the Indian subcontinent was occupied by Indo- Aryans. Most of the Aryans then were pastoralists. Milk provided for their food and other products like butter and curd. The Vedas have emphasized the connection between spirituality and the choice of food without relinquishing the need for taste and health. Food culture has a vibrant history filled with tasty twists and turns, which is in agreement with the claim that Indian culture can be explored through its foods. In fact, across many cultures, one can historically trace socio-cultural reasons behind culinary choices. Tracing the history of food in India is pivotal to understanding Indian cuisine.

Recent research throws light on linguistic similarities of food items consumed across cultures making it slightly easier to connect the finer dots of Indian cuisine from the Vedic era. The Aryans considered food to be a gift from God and a source of strength. In the four Vedas, Rigveda, Samaveda, Yajurveda, and Atharvaveda, there are various mentions of the grains used during those times. Initially, barley was a staple food of most Aryans. Cultivation of other crops such as wheat, sugarcane, and millets followed. Lentils, mainly red, green, and black, were also grown. Later, the Aryans added rice and other cereals to their diet.

The structural embodiments of the caste system, a legitimised practice of inequity believed to be inherited through one's parentage and occupation, engendered a sense of purity in the culinary and consumption habits of people. Brahmins, the upper caste priests, often adhered to vegetarian food habits led by the philosophy of sattva. In contrast, Shudras, the lowest group in the caste ladder, engaged in eating animal meat and other kinds of tamasic habits. The possibility of upper caste politics to portray certain kinds of food habits as

superior to others could be indeed the case. It is possible that the caste system was strengthened with the help of systemic food demonization. Unfortunately, the caste system continues to shape food habits even in present times.

SCHEMES AND PROGRAMMES IN INDIA

In India, the food sector is regulated and managed through various government departments and organisations at both state and central levels. These departments oversee food safety, quality, production, distribution and policy formulation. The Government entities related to foods in India include:

1. THE MID DAY MEAL SCHEME: IMPLEMENTATION BY FORMER CM. K. KAMARAJ

Midday Meal Scheme was first launched in Tamil Nadu, pioneered by the former Chief minister K. Kamaraj in the early 1960s. And now (21st century) this scheme is still in practice which aims to eliminate hunger among school going children's and also promote the education.

He decided to provide free noon meal to poor children in all primary schools across the state. It is aimed to uplift the children from the most underserved communities in india. This scheme is also to promote education and motivating the school education. Now Free and compulsory education also emphasized by the government.

FURTHER INITIATIVES TAKEN BY M.G. R (NUTRITIOUS MEAL PROGRAMME)

Education lays the foundation for the development of a society and hunger becomes an impediment to learning. Keeping this vision, the Nutritious Meal Programme was introduced by the then Chief Minister Puratchi Thalaivar Dr. M.G.R. on 01.07.1982. The Nutritious Meal Programme was introduced for the Children in the age groups of 2 to 5 years in anganwadi and 5 to 9 years in primary schools. The scheme was extended to urban areas with effect from 15.09.1982 and further extended to all the children in the age group of 10-15 years from 15.09.1984.

CONTEMPORARY APPLICATION OF THE SCHEME BY STALIN:

Apart from the noon meal scheme, In September 2022, Chief Minister M.K. Stalin launched the 'Chief Minister's Breakfast Scheme' to further combat hunger and nutritional deficiencies among schoolchildren. This initiative provides free breakfast to students in government-run schools, aiming to improve attendance, concentration, and overall health. The scheme has been lauded as a model for other states, reinforcing Tamil Nadu's commitment to social welfare and education.

This scheme has certain main objectives like

- To provide adequate nutrition to economically disadvantaged children.
- To combat malnutrition among the children and to increase their literacy rate.

CHIEF MINISTERS BREAKFAST SCHEME:

Announcement has been made by the Hon'ble Chief Minister of Tamil Nadu on 07.05.2022 under Rule 110 that Breakfast will be provided to primary school children from 1st to 5th standard studying in Government schools on all school working days and the scheme has been launched on 15.09.2022 at Madurai by the Hon'ble Chief Minister of Tamil Nadu. In the first phase, Corporations, Municipalities and Panchayats were selected based on high prevalence of Anaemia as per NHFS-5 data, economically backward blocks as per SBGF, habitations of Tribal population and inaccessibility of the areas, will be covered under this scheme. At present 1,14,095 primary school children studying in 1545 Government schools will be covered under the scheme at a total cost of Rs.33.56 crores which will be extended to remaining schools in phased manner. This scheme followed some food menu in the schools. There are given below:

MONDAY- Uppuma type (rava uppuma, vermicelli uppuma, rice uppuma with vegetable sambhar)

TUESDAY- Kitchadi type (rava vegetable kitchadi, sorghum vegetable kitchadi)

WEDNESDAY- Pongal type (rava Pongal with vegetable sambhar)

THURSDAY- Uppuma type (rice uppuma with wheat rava uppuma with vegetable sambhar)

FRIDAY- Sweet type (sweet pongal, rava kesari and vermicelli kesari)

The quantity of raw material will be 50 grams per child per day. Locally available Millet based Breakfast also be utilized for atleast 2 days a week. This will ensure approximately 293.40 calories of energy, 9.85 grams of Protein, 5.91 grams of Fat, 1.64grms of iron and 20.41 grams of calcium for each child.

FOOD SAFETY AND STANDARDS AUTHORITY OF INDIA:

Food Safety and Standards Authority of India (FSSAI) is an autonomous statutory body established under the Food Safety and Standards Act, 2006 (FSS Act). Ministry of Health & Family Welfare, Government of India is the administrative Ministry of FSSAI.

The Food Safety and Standards Act 2006 states:

An Act to consolidate the laws relating to food and to establish the Food Safety and Standards Authority of India for laying down science-based standards for articles of food and to regulate their manufacture, storage, distribution, sale and import, to ensure availability of safe and wholesome food for human consumption and for matters connected therewith or incidental there to many important initiatives have also been taken by FSSAI keeping in mind food safety and standards. Following are few of these important initiatives:

- **Eat Right India** – The aim is not just to provide food to one and all, but to provide quality food to everyone. With this initiative, FSSAI intends to make good quality food accessible to every citizen of the country

- **Clean Street Food** – This involves training the street food vendors and making them aware of the violations as per the FSS Act 2006. This will also help in the social and economic upliftment of street food vendors
 - **Diet for Life** – This is another initiative taken by FSSAI, to spread awareness about metabolic disorders.
4. **Save Food, Share Food, Share Joy** – Encouraging people to avoid food wastage and promote food donation. Through this, FSSAI intends to connect food- collecting agencies with the food-producing companies and share the food with the ones in need.
 5. **MINISTRY OF FOOD PROCESSING INDUSTRIES:**

It is a federal ministry of the **GOVERNMENT OF INDIA** responsible for the formulation and administration of the rules, regulations and laws relating to food processing in India. It was established in 1988 and plays a strategic role and functions in Policy support developmental and promotional aspect, Technical, advisory and Regulatory aspects. Better utilization, value addition of agricultural produce for enhancement of income of farmers and Induction of modern technology into the food processing industries from both domestic and external sources are some goals of this Industry. A strong and dynamic food processing sector plays a vital role in reduction in the wastage of perishable agricultural produce, enhancing shelf life of food products, ensuring value addition to agricultural produce, diversification & commercialization of agriculture, generation of employment, enhancing income of farmers and creating surplus for the export of Agro & processed foods. In the era of economic liberalization, all segments including; private, public and co-operative sectors have defined roles to play and the Ministry promotes their active participation.

The Ministry of Food Processing Industries has a clear goal of attaining these objectives by facilitating and acting as a catalyst to attract quality

investments from within India and abroad into this sector with the aim of making food processing a national initiative. With this overall objective, the Ministry aims to:

- Enhance farmer's income by better utilization and value addition of agricultural produce
- Minimize wastage at all stages in the food processing chain by the development of infrastructure for storage, transportation and processing of agro-food produce;
- Introduce of modern technology into the food processing industries from both domestic and external sources;
- Provide policy support, and support for creation of Infrastructure, capacity expansion/ Upgradation and other supportive measures form the growth of the sectors;
- Promote export of processed food products.

6. DEPARTMENT OF FOOD AND PUBLIC DISTRIBUTION:

PDS (Public distribution System) was introduced around World War II as a war-time rationing measure. Before the 1960s, distribution through PDS was generally dependent on imports of food grains. It was expanded in the 1960s as a response to the food shortages of the time; subsequently, the government set up the Agriculture Prices Commission and the FCI to improve domestic procurement and storage of food grains for PDS and by the 1970s, PDS had evolved into a universal scheme for the distribution of subsidized food.

The Central and State Governments share responsibilities in order to provide food grains to the identified beneficiaries. The Centre procures food grains from farmers at a minimum support price (MSP) and sells it to states at central issue prices. It is responsible for transporting the grains to godowns in each state. States bear the responsibility of transporting food grains from these godowns to each fair price shop (ration shop), where the beneficiary

buys the food grains at the lower central issue price. Many states further subsidies the price of food grains before selling it to beneficiaries. PDS is one of the biggest welfare programmes of the government, helping farmers sell their produce at remunerative prices as well as the poorer sections of society to buy food grains at affordable rates. Its effectiveness can be enhanced with **technology based solutions** as it evident from some of the states’ successes towards the same. Shifting towards DBT is another idea, but with caution.

**COMPARISON TABLE OF VEDIC AND 21ST CENTURY
 FOOD PRACTICES:**

Aspect	Vedic Food Culture & Practices	21st Century Food Culture & Practices
Food Philosophy	Food is sacred (Prasad), consumed with gratitude.	Food is convenience-driven, often taken for pleasure or comfort.
Meal Preparation	Home-cooked, slow, mindful preparation with fresh ingredients.	Ready-to-eat, fast food, microwave meals, processed ingredients.
Fasting practices	Fasting (Ekadashi, Navratri, etc.) for detox and spiritual growth.	Intermittent fasting for weight loss and fitness trends.
Community and sharing	Food shared in community gatherings, served to guests and the needy.	Individualistic eating habits, takeout culture, food delivery apps.
Ayurvedic influence.	Eating as per body type (Doshas – Vata, Pitta, Kapha)	Diets based on calorie counting, macros, and modern nutrition.

Types of meals.	Simple, balanced meals with sattvic (pure) foods.	Complex, highly processed meals with artificial ingredients.
Connection to nature.	Seasonal, local, organic produce, farm-to-table.	Packaged, frozen, and imported foods available year-round.

POLITICIZATION OF FOOD ON THE INFLUENCE OF CASTE AND RELIGION DURING VEDIC PERIOD

Food is one of the most common and powerful caste markers in Indian society. Ever since, India was never considered as a vegetarian country. During vedic period non vegetarianism was common, even ayurveda which we regard now as purely Hindu vegetarian phenomenon advocated remedies based on meat. The popularity of vegetarianism emerged from the Jain, rather than Hindu tradition even Buddhism did not insist on vegetarianism. The early vedic period divided people intentionally through categorizing what people should eat based on their caste. The vedic constitutional document (Manusmriti) established the order and occupation of four major caste groups and the arrival of varna system, a hymn in the Rigveda, which is the oldest veda that portrays the Brahmana (Priest), the kshatriya (Noble), The Vyshiya (Commoner), and the Shudra (Servant). Panchamas were so called as untouchables and impure. Therefore, the food was thus bifurcated amongst the four varnas as pure, impure, veg and non-veg.

When taken in **RELIGIOUS** aspect, many Hindus follow a vegetarian diet due to beliefs in ahimsa (non-violence) and the sanctity of life. This influences dietary practices in terms of avoiding meat, especially beef, as cows are considered sacred in Hinduism. In some parts of India, certain foods are also avoided during religious fasting or observance of festivals, namely garlic, onions and other vegetables.

In **Islam**, food laws are outlined in the Quran and Hadith. Halal dietary laws govern what is permissible to eat, such as the prohibition of pork and the requirement that meat be slaughtered according to specific guidelines (zabiha). Alcohol is also forbidden in Islamic dietary practices.

In **Christianity** they may have dietary restrictions tied to religious observances, such as fasting periods during Lent or avoiding certain foods like meat on Fridays in some denominations. However, the extent to which dietary restrictions are followed varies widely among different Christian sects.

Many **Buddhists** follow a vegetarian diet due to their commitment to non-violence (ahimsa) and compassion for all living beings. Some Buddhist traditions, like those practiced in certain parts of Southeast Asia, also emphasize avoiding foods that are considered overly stimulating, such as garlic or onions.

- **PURITY AND POLLUTION:**

The concept of “pakka” and “kaccha” food marked the major divisions between upper and lower caste because of their difference in ingredients such as ghee and water. The idea of caste purity sometimes extends to the food one consumed with others. Members of different castes may not share meals due to concerns over contamination or maintaining caste boundaries. Certain foods were also considered “pure” and “impure” based on caste status. Higher castes, particularly Brahmins, may avoid foods that are seen as impure or linked to lower castes, such as meat from animals that are deemed unclean. Lower castes, especially those historically labeled as “untouchables,” have often been restricted to consuming foods that are considered polluted by the higher castes.

- **POLITICS BEHIND CONSUMING MEAT:**

The politics of meat consumption is a complex and often contentious issue, influenced by ethics, economics, culture, environmental concerns, and government policies. Global meat markets are impacted by trade policies, with some nations imposing tariffs or banning imported meat for economic or health reasons. Governments subsidize the production of meat, making it more affordable and accessible. Industrial meat producers frequently receive tax breaks, while small-scale farmers may face competition. Meat consumption is deeply tied to cultural identity, traditions, and religious beliefs and some countries or regions view vegetarianism/veganism as a "Western" or elite concept, creating political and social divides. Religious dietary laws such as halal and kosher are also the factors into meat-related policies and regulations.

The cow and vegetarianism: A common misconception in the modern times is that the early Vedic Aryans attributed a sacredness to the cow based on a desire for cow protection, thus giving the religion a symbol that is threatened by anyone who consumes beef. There are several reasons behind the non-consumption of beef by Hindu's especially brahmins, Brahmins abstaining from beef was in response to a famine. As the most powerful caste, they eased tensions with the starving masses by adopting a partially vegetarian diet. During a period of territorial expansion, in 5 CE, into Southern India, Brahmins travelled with their armies and a small herd of cattle. This was the first time they prohibited cow slaughter for two major reasons. First, they had a lot of land to cover; and second, they established their Brahminical superiority through a rejection of local dietary practice. thereby introducing to southern India to a version of Hinduism where vegetarian Brahmins led the most meritorious, righteous lives. This would give rise to arguably some of the most conservative Brahmin cultures in the present-day Tamil Nadu and Karnataka. Whereas in the North, Brahmins continued to consume beef well into the 18th century. Even requiring it for certain religious rituals. Over the

centuries that followed, this system became an accepted way of life across the country, despite certain Brahmin communities maintaining a diet that included fish, like in Bengal or meat in Kashmir and Kerala. In spite of, all this, beef was consumed by Dalits due to many reasons such as: accessibility, affordability and for health benefits.

Pork and beef became part of the Dalit cuisine as it was easily available because the upper castes didn't consume it. Hindu caste hierarchy puts pure vegetarian Brahmins at the top, non-beef-eating non-vegetarians in the middle and beef-eaters at the absolute bottom. A recent national survey found that over 70 per cent of people that eat beef are from the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes, 21 per cent are from other backward castes and only 7 per cent belong to upper castes.

Further, given that beef is the cheapest protein in India, it is a significant source of nutrition for those unable to afford more expensive meats. Since the caste-system encompasses all aspects of one's professional, personal and spiritual life this consumption perpetually keeps Dalits who consume beef bound to the bottom of the Hindu system.

“Rousseau and Food” article was written by Kelly Oliver, Department of Philosophy, Vanderbilt University, Nashville, TN, USA. Jean Jacques Rousseau, a political philosopher was very concerned with food and diet. He said, a wholesome diet leads to a wholesome character. He gives more importance to a vegetarian diet. He said that “we are what we eat” like savages eat wild animals, that is why they are wild and civilized men eat cultivated grain, that is why they become cultivated. He said that freedom to eat should be given to everyone, but because of the society and state pressures, we are bound to eat what they give us. His main motto was that if we eat good food, we become good people.

ROLE OF AGRICULTURE IN FOOD POLITICS DURING VEDIC PERIOD

The vedic civilisation can be categorized into later and early vedic period. In its earliest stages, Vedic civilization was semi-nomadic, particularly between 1500 BCE—1000 BCE, and relied on a mix of agriculture and pastoral economy to survive. During this period, the primary agricultural crops continued to be wheat varieties and barley. Historians observe that the early Aryan migrants' nomadic lifestyles gave way to a more settled one in the later Vedic period, about roughly 1000 BCE. Even while cattle continued to play a significant role in Vedic culture, a semi-nomadic way of living was insufficient to support an expanding population. As a consequence, Vedic society started to shift from a semi-nomadic lifestyle to a settled one as it grew in size. Families started to establish permanent residences as agriculture gained importance.

Agriculture became the main source of income though cattle rearing was prominent during vedic period. This was the main objective why Hindus prohibited slaughtering of cow. The Aryan nomads were meat-eating warriors and herders before they turned farmers. Conversely, today's popular Hindu discourse idealises an agrarian lifestyle and the vegetarian Brahmin, only makes patronising concessions for the upper castes who eat meat, but not for anybody who eats beef. The vegetarian ideals in India are myopic, as it exalts the cow while literally milking it for all its worth. The hyper consumption and religious postulation of dairy, specifically of ghee and milk, has facilitated the growth of inhumane and problematic dairy and leather industries. It is noble to revere and protect the cow while the animal is dairy cattle. However, killing, skinning, consuming or disposing of the animal are impure acts.

POLITICIZATION OF FOOD IN 21ST CENTURY

Despite all measures taken to eliminate caste discrimination, the practice still exists in contemporary society. This is applied to food from production to consumption. Even in the contemporary era there are many sections of people who hesitate to eat food from one's home who cooks beef. So, such conservative mindset still exists due to sacredness. We would like to dwell upon the initiatives, welfare measures taken up by government and the influence of government in food consumption in 21st century food politics.

GOVERNMENTS INTERVENTIONS IN FOOD POLICY

Nation-states became central to food governance through policies, subsidies, and trade agreements. Social movements and ideologies via socialism and capitalism influenced food distribution systems (e.g. Public Distribution system in India). Government came forward with several schemes for children's enrolling at government schools by providing them nutritious food and the foundation of "AMMA UNAVAGAM" is beneficial for common people. There is also politics behind the food supplied by the government.

- **Removal of eggs from mid-day meals in school:**

"To provide healthy food to students across the state, the government of Maharashtra has introduced eggs and bananas and also finalized a new menu," said school education minister Deepak Kesarkar when he announced the decision on November 7, 2023. A month later, the ruling parties' spiritual cells appeared to have suddenly woken up to its perceived ramifications, as Acharya Tushar Bhosale, chief of the BJP spiritual cell, and Akshay Bhosale, chief of the Dharmveer Spiritual Sena, wrote separately to Shinde in opposing the decision. Since all of these groups abstain from eating non-vegetarian food, the school education department's

decision to offer eggs has offended the religious feelings of several Hindu sects, including the Brahmins and Jains, according to Acharya Tushar Bhosale. "If eggs are offered, there's a chance a child from a strictly vegetarian household would inadvertently consume them, harming the family's custom and religious feelings. Other than eggs, the government can provide children with wholesome food in the form of dry fruit, cow milk, and jaggery-peanuts. This happened not only in Maharashtra but also to Gujarat, Haryana, Punjab, Rajasthan and many more due to political influence.

- **Politics behind Public Distribution System:**

The politics behind the Public Distribution System (PDS) often revolve around its potential as both a welfare measure and a political tool. PDS, which provides essential commodities like rice, wheat, sugar, and kerosene to the population of below poverty line at subsidized rates, is a critical component of social welfare in many countries, particularly India. Subsidized food distribution through PDS is a key strategy for gaining the support of lower-income and marginalized groups. Political parties often leverage it to appeal for votes in elections and sometimes announce additional benefits through PDS, such as free rice or enhanced subsidies, as part of their election manifestos. Strong popular mobilizations demanding a "Right to Food" policy in many countries have argued that food-based social assistance was not just a social and economic right, but an entitlement that is essential to "achieving economic democracy, without which political democracy is at best incomplete"

INFLUENCE OF GOVERNMENT ON CONSUMPTION OF FOOD

The government of the neighboring state of Maharashtra, banned cattle slaughter and beef sales, so as to establish Hindutva ideology. Many lower-caste and non-Hindus was largely affected by this decision because beef is

cheaper than chicken, goat or lamb. It has been said that Indian cuisine is not homogeneous because food habits and eating practices differs because of caste, religions and regional lines. 80 per cent of Indians are non-vegetarians but government enforces the citizens to become vegetarian. Government wants to establish their ideology. Government overlooks the nutritional benefits of non- vegetarian food. In March 2015, the Maharashtra government banned beef, and it affected Dalits and Muslims largely.

The government also banned the consumption of meat for eight days during Jain community monasticism. It shows the food politics seen at social, political and economic level. In October 2015, Lal Manohar, Chief Minister of Haryana said that if Muslim wants to live in this state, then they have to abstain from eating beef. But when this issue becomes politicize then he denied this statement as “According to me everyone has a right to eat whatever they like to eat, hence there should be no boundaries”. Politicians should not do their dirty politics on the basic need of the food. In September 2015, the case of Dadri near Ghaziabad was highlighted in which, a man was killed because of consuming cow meat, but it was not true. He was a Muslim who ate only meat but some stranger disseminated false information claiming that he ate beef. The Hindu Brahmins, became rage as the worship cows and ended up in killing them, the actual case wasn't interrogated. such inhuman behaviour still exists in this 21st century which portrays the worst social structure. Politicians highlighted this issue, for seeking the attention of the public. With earlier knowledge we know that Shudra category was denied to eat prashad in temples and they were also denied to get proper food. As a result, we could say that the governance and the people is responsible for the miserable condition of food politics in India.

INTERVENTION OF POLITICS IN STREET FOOD

Street food is particularly integral to social structure and group interaction for the country which is religiously significant and universally important yet strikingly different between cultures. Indian street food's wide variation, economic heft, and importance to daily life make it a particularly effective tool for political or religious groups in India to increase their social influence. Street food is more popular in India where majority of the population consume across all age groups. They run behind the aroma of food cart on the street rather preferring to dine in restaurants or hotels. Many Indian families derive their livelihood from selling their own version of a favorite street snack. Street food vendors represent a significant portion of the informal sector of India's economy, which employs more than ninety percent of the country's workers. Additionally, street food in India is as diverse as it is ubiquitous. In contemporary era the food cart is being spotted in every corner of the street. Earlier street foods were meant only for poor population due to its affordability without any GST but now majority of the populations go to spot has become food carts which provides delectable and affordable foods. The beggars of India and population below the poverty line survive with the existence of food carts on the street. Thus, the boom of street food business against the restaurants and hotels is much debatable now.

- **Concept of hygiene in street food:**

Some people in India also avoid street food stalls in concern of hygiene standards followed by vendors. They feel fearful of sanitation, quality, and surroundings. However, street food stalls usually serve a preponderance of the population in a city. Moreover, street food vendors across India suffer from displacement on a daily basis. They can also suffer from legal sanctions and have depleted constitutional recognition. Additionally, according to Anne Dahmen, a German research scholar and

coordinator for the sustainable Hyderabad Project (SHP), eviction possibilities are high for street vendors because of a lack of awareness about the standard protocols and requirements in following the Food Safety and Standards Act 2006. However, Anne Dahmen also states that the perception and overall situation of street food surrounding uncertainty can be improved by the government by managing the sector better, by regulating the process to be more participatory. This industry has grown and preserved economies in the country.

According to a media report, if street food stalls fold permanently, then the high cost to be beared by a customer and effort to find food which has similar value would be difficult. Furthermore, according to Anne Dahmen, if proper training based on legalities, hygiene, and preparation is administered by different authorities through various schemes to various street vendors across India, then the street food industry can be pillars of sustenance for societies.

Conclusively, though some people in India avoid street food because of hygiene purposes, it's role in sustaining and shaping the Indian food economy remains unparalleled. Additionally, though some of the street vendors are at risk of eviction on a daily basis, they are also the lifeblood of freshness and taste in taste buds across different cities in India. Consequently, with the right schemes of training programs provided by the government to street vendors, there can be a possibility for crucial advancement in institutional awareness concerning culinary legalities, acts, and hygiene practices.

INITIATIVES TAKEN BY THE GOVERNMENT OF INDIA TO STREET FOOD BUSINESS

Governments may impose strict licensing requirements, health inspections, and zoning laws that determine where and how street vendors can

operate. Some policies favour established businesses by making it difficult for street vendors to obtain permits, forcing them to operate illegally or under constant threat of eviction. The Street Vendors (Protection of Livelihood and Regulation of street vending) Act on 1st May, 2014 which is also applicable for street food vendors. It was hailed as a forward-looking legislation that aimed to uplift street vendors by legalising their vending rights. However, the legislation has been encountering significant hurdles in its practical execution. Clean Street Food is one of the initiatives taken up by FSSAI under a 360-degree approach to Food Safety and Healthy Nutrition. This would involve training and capacity building of the street food vendors and ensure proper regulatory oversight over them under the Food Safety and Standards Act, 2006. Its major objective focus to ensure health, hygiene and safety standard of street food for all consumers, to ensure social and economic upliftment of street vendor community by helping them in improving quality of offerings thereby attracting more customers and to enhance the popularity of Street food by transforming it into a global brand by itself.

Role and Contribution of the Public :

The public plays a crucial and multifaceted role in the politics and business of street food. As primary consumers, their tastes, preferences, and purchasing power directly shape the demand and diversity of street food offerings. Public patronage determines which vendors succeed and how street food cultures evolve in different regions. Beyond consumption, the public also influences street food politics through activism and civic engagement—advocating for hygienic practices, fair regulations, and the protection of street vendors' rights. In many cities, community support has been instrumental in resisting unjust evictions of vendors and in pushing for inclusive urban policies that recognize street food as a vital part of local economies and cultural heritage. Moreover, through social media and reviews, the public can amplify visibility for vendors, impacting their economic viability and shaping public discourse

around food safety, urban space, and informal economies. Thus, the public's role extends beyond consumption to active participation in shaping the narrative, policies, and sustainability of the street food ecosystem.

SUGGESTIONS

The suggestions of our project dwells into a positive change in the society on the basis of production and consumption of food by Policy Recommendations to increase Support for Local Farmers in Advocating the policies that provide subsidies or incentives for small-scale and sustainable farming , Improve Food Labelling Laws to Push for clearer, standardized labels on food products regarding GMOs, additives, and nutritional value, Expand Food Assistance Programs such as universal school meals, and local food banks to address food insecurity and Regulate Big Food Lobbying to Promote transparency in corporate influence on food policies and public health guidelines.

To eliminate hunger among the population, the Government of India should come up with more programmes and initiatives in the upcoming years. Most importantly caste and religion influence towards the consumption of food should be eradicated and the consumption should be highly focused on healthy and tasty aspects. To build a more equitable and sustainable food future, policymakers, businesses, and consumers must take collective action. By advocating for ethical sourcing, supporting local farmers, reducing waste, and implementing policies that prioritize health and sustainability.

CONCLUSION

Politization of food in India a complex and dynamic subject influenced by different factors, including government policies, economic conditions, social structure and the influence of religion, caste and community. Despite all the factors that leads to the politics behind food, there is room for positive change and let people to consume food based on their own interest rather than

insisting them to eat in respect to their beliefs. The government should also involve only on the positive notion when it comes to food, concerning about the health and hygiene of the people. We can also witness the changes that happened in recent years between vegetarian and non-vegetarian on the basis of consumption. The number of pure veg restaurant is reducing as the non veg consumption is hitting up in majority. In contemporary modern world, consuming food on the basis of caste and community has been reduced, as most brahmins consume meat and others apart from Muslims, SC and ST's are also consuming beef.

The initiatives taken up by the government of India, on food security is substantial to discuss. "Public Distribution System" which provides food grains and other supplements to particular section of the society and the already mentioned AMMA UNAVAGAM is also a appreciable initiative by the government which aims to eradicate the hunger pain. The National Food Security Act (NFSA) aims to ensure food accessibility, challenges like food wastage, malnutrition, farmer distress, and price fluctuations continue to persist.

Finally, we wish to conclude our project on how food politics in India is interconnected with FOOD SECURITY. The most challenging problem in today's world is food insecurity, an estimated approximately 832 million people around the world suffer from a lack of adequate and healthy food on a regular basis for their life. This problem is likely to intensify around the world due to high political risk and weak institutions. It is the responsibility of the government to provide good health conditions to its population.

Annexures

Various State Foods

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- Does the caste and religion affect the access to food in India?
- Does Government putforth effective policies and initiatives to eliminate inequality in the consumption of food?
- Is their any change in the production of food between vedic period and 21st century?
- Do Politics intervene in street food business?

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